

Study On The Influencing Factors And Mechanism of University Students' Online Learning Behavior: A Case Study Of Newly-built Universities in Hebei Province

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Abstract

Regarding the characteristics of online learning behavior, scholars pay more attention to the characteristics that are different from the traditional education model under the online education model. Some scholars conduct research with a limited population and compare the findings obtained from the survey to derive the corresponding characteristics and features. Through the comparative analysis and behavioral summary, scholars understood the demands of both developers and users, and gave some suggestions for further improving technologies and services to make learners have better e-learning experiences and enhance the effectiveness. This gives some reference to further improve the technology and service to make learners have better e-learning experience and enhance the effect.

Introduction

Zhao Hong et al. (2012) focus more on the characteristics of online learners' psychological regulation, skill development, and learning mode in the learning process, and they generally select randomly selected respondents to conduct empirical studies to analyze and summarize the characteristics of these aspects. Li, Guomin et al. (2001) compared the differences between online and traditional learning methods and summarized some characteristics, i.e., e-learning behaviors are characterized by high skill, professionalism, virtualization, autonomy, and globalization, etc.

Influencing factors of e-learning behavior

Through literature reading and synthesis, the author found that there are two types of factors influencing e-learning behavior, one is the internal influence related to the scholars themselves, and the other is the influence from external changes. The sources of internal influence are attitudes, strategies, satisfaction, behavioral persistence, psychological regulation, etc., while the influence of external changes comes from technical support, the restriction of time and space, and the difficulty of operating the online system.

Researchers have mainly verified the influencing factors of online learning behavior through both literature analysis and empirical studies. The studies of theoretical analysis are based on the theory of learning conditions and the theory of elements of teaching system, and the influencing factors are grouped into four aspects: learners, instructors, online courses, and learning environment, which are categorized for verification and investigation; empirical analysis is based on constructivist theory and scholars' modeling analysis, which generally study The empirical analysis is based on constructivist theory and scholars' modeling analysis, and generally studies the correlation between psychological factors or external influences such as learning attitudes, learning strategies, self-efficacy, technical support, learning tools, and learning effects or satisfaction, as well as the degree of influence, and then summarizes the influencing factors of online learning and constructs a new correlation model.

Model of online learning behavior

Referring to the research ideas of foreign scholars, many domestic scholars' research on online learning behavior is based on the construction of models, which are easier to study and visually reflect the essence, connotation and influencing factors of online learning behavior than theoretical research.

A representative modeling study includes: Dr. Peng Wenhui (2012) used the rational behavior model as the basis and built a model with nine potential factor variables, and conducted a survey by distributing questionnaires to students in several universities. In addition, Dr. Peng also developed a model to describe the rich connotation of online education, which visually presents the characteristics of behavioral performance of

online teaching. Zhou Yan et al. (2009) first summarized and concluded the characteristics of college students' online learning behavior, and established their own model of online learning behavior based on the reference and analysis of TRA model and TAM model, and analyzed that "the ease of use and availability of online learning tools and resources have significant effects on school students' attitudes and satisfaction of online learning, and the strength of learning motivation and self-efficacy have significant effects on school students' attitudes and satisfaction of online learning. The analysis concluded that "the ease of use and availability of online learning tools and resources have a significant impact on students' attitude and satisfaction of online learning, the strength of learning motivation and self-efficacy have a significant impact on students' willingness to learn online, and the tendency of online learning of students is influenced by their own psychological factors and external environmental conditions".

Status of foreign research

Foreign scholars pay more attention to the basic research on online learning behavior, for example, their research on the definition and characteristics focuses on the description of the characteristics and laws of behavior and the process and characteristics analysis based on the establishment of models, while the representation of behavior mostly adopts the method of model building. In terms of learning patterns, most foreign scholars' studies are conducted by uploading records in real time through tools and software, and then analyzing and summarizing their operating habits and preferences when learning online; foreign scholars conduct studies on influencing factors, mostly from the perspective of the recipients, analyzing their cognition and feelings, and generally adopting questionnaires, network records and observations, and conversations with respondents. They generally adopt questionnaires, network records, and conversations with respondents to observe and explore users' participation and personal preferences, and then compare the results with previous hypotheses.

The author summarizes the relevant recent foreign studies as follows: P. Hsieh (2013) identified self-efficacy as a key component of successful online learning in his article "Open online learning experience: self-efficacy and satisfaction in online learning", and the study identified five levels of self-efficacy in online learning: completing online courses, interacting with online community peers, handling course tools, interaction with the instructor, academic interaction with classmates and corresponding satisfaction with online learning. H. Finger (2011) in an empirical study of metacognitive strategies and online learning behaviors explored the relationship between metacognitive strategies and online learning behaviors and test scores through the return of over 900 validated questionnaires, suggesting recommendations for the development of online learning competencies. J. Lee (2014) in "Online learning with tasks" examined course completion and satisfaction of online learning triggered by different tasks to explore the criteria for grading effective tasks in online learning. J. Enuan (2012) in "Collaborative online learning motivates learning: analyzing learners' online learning experiences" reflected on the lack of learner collaboration in online learning systems, exploring how to establish social model of online learning and how to develop a culture of distance education.

2.1.3 Research Review

1 Progress of Existing Research

The study of college students' online learning behavior shows a trend of multidisciplinary convergence: as an interdisciplinary topic, the study of college students' online learning behavior has attracted the attention of scholars from many disciplines, such as anthropology, management, education, and psychology, and has also emerged the research on "learning adaptability in online learning space", "effective student learning in online learning environment", and "effective student learning in online learning environment". The research on similar topics such as "effective learning behavior of students in online learning environment", "factors influencing learning engagement in online learning space", and "interactive behavior" has also emerged. Diverse theoretical bases and research perspectives from different disciplines have continuously enriched the study of college students' online learning behavior, which provide a high theoretical starting point and research inspiration for this study.

The research on the influencing factors of college students' online learning behavior has made initial achievements: the early research on college students' online learning behavior was mainly at the stage of conceptual development and theoretical construction, and it was only in the late 1990s that scholars gradually expanded to the empirical research on the antecedent and outcome variables of college students' online learning behavior as the psychological and cognitive factors of college students' online learning behavior were gradually highlighted. In terms of influencing factors, most of the studies point out that supportive, innovative, and pedagogical faculty behaviors, faculty-student trust, and an organizational culture that is open and encourages experimentation have a facilitating effect on college students' online learning behaviors. Such studies are supported by both theoretical derivations, quantitative questionnaire data, and some in-depth case studies. Although the research subjects are less directly targeted at college students in new local undergraduate institutions, the findings and research methods also provide useful references for this study.

2 Limitations of the study to be improved

(1) The phenomenon of "theoretical jungle" emerged in the study: "theoretical jungle" is Koontz's description of the chaotic situation of the management theory research in the 1860s, in which there were many different opinions and confusion. Drawing on this expression, the "theory jungle" phenomenon in this study refers to the fact that the current research on college students' online learning behavior is still vague and overly generalized. This is reflected in the fact that the research on college students' online learning behavior is still mixed with the research on students' personal development and learning platforms, and the research does not highlight the special characteristics of online learning behavior and the culture of college students as a group. In different literatures, "online learning behavior" is used to describe all aspects of college students' learning activities in the Internet, which makes researchers not agree on key questions such as what is online learning behavior, how and why it occurs. The lack of conceptual clarity has also created difficulties for empirical research in this area and confusion for educational administrators in promoting college students' online learning behaviors in the practice process. This is partly due to the lack of understanding of the nature of college students' online learning behavior, and partly due to the fact that researchers from different disciplines have proposed different epistemologies, goals and processes from their own perspectives, so college students' online learning behavior has become a "Rorschach inkblot test" in management research.

(2) The research content needs to be further deepened: the online learning behavior of college students is the result of the interaction between the actors and the external environment, and the complex relationship presented in the interaction process makes the study of college students' online learning behavior need both a wide-angle lens to take in the overall picture and a microscope to see the details and complexity of its operation, and it needs both top-down macroscopic grasp and bottom-up microscopic exploration. Research on college students' online learning behavior is scattered across the domains of student personal development, teaching and learning, organizational learning, and learning platforms. The enthusiasm of scholars is growing and has attracted the attention of researchers from different disciplines, but the existing studies have focused more on "philosophical levels, macro themes, and fragmented phenomena rather than the details of practice in real situations." Most of the research has focused on the overall picture and top-down macro studies, but less on the micro exploration of operational details. The early studies mainly argued the importance of college students' online learning behavior at the contingency level. Empirical studies on college students' online learning behavior have been increasing since the 2000s, but the studies mainly focus on the influence of external environmental factors on college students' online learning behavior, and the research direction is relatively single, and there is a lack of discussion on how the influencing factors act on college students' online learning behavior. The existing studies lack explanations for the dynamic changes in the longitudinal time dimension of college students' online learning behaviors, which are insufficient to fully understand the many complex characteristics of college students' online learning behaviors and tend to ignore more rich facts. These make one wonder whether the existing studies risk simplifying the complex phenomenon of college students' online learning behavior.

(3) Lack of Chinese perspective in the research field: China has a rich practice in college students' online learning behavior, but there are few localized theoretical contributions in this field, and a large number of research results are cited in the West. College students' online learning behavior is a highly complex and multifaceted socialization process that is influenced by a combination of social relationships and technical support at the macro level of the organization, as well as individual interrelationships and student motivation at the micro level, and is difficult to separate from the sociocultural context in which it occurs. For example, despite continuous social change, China is still a society where organizational members are very sensitive to hierarchical relationships. Students are accustomed to obeying the decisions of their teachers and rarely exercise independent thought and judgment. Students' learning attitudes and behaviors are greatly influenced by their school teachers. Both socio-cultural and educational management systems may make the factors of school teachers, teacher-student trust and student motivation that influence college students' online learning behavior in China and their mechanisms of action on college students' online learning behavior different from those in the West. If these issues are not addressed and Western research results are directly cited, researchers will not be able to contribute a unique Chinese perspective to enrich the knowledge in the field of college students' online learning behavior, but will easily fall into the fad of "enthusiasm at the beginning, then widespread dissemination, then gradual disappointment, and finally abandonment". It is a short-lived management fad.

Theoretical Foundations

Social Exchange Theory

Social Exchange Theory (SET) is a psychological theory founded by Homans to explain human social behavior based on economically relevant concepts. The social exchange theory believes that people are absolutely rational, and that human behavior is based on the rewards and rewards that can be brought by the implementation of the behavior, and the fact that the behavior requires effort to measure, and choose the higher reward to implement the behavior, or to exchange, through the superiority of the exchange object to choose the best exchange, is a kind of calculation of gain and loss and benefit risk behavior. In other words, people will compare the benefits of their own behavior and the price paid, if the price is less than the benefit, the exchange

behavior will continue, if the benefit is less than the price, the exchange will be terminated. In this way, the essence of human social activities is attributed to exchange, and all social relationships arising from exchange are understood as exchange relationships. The social exchange theory considers exchange behavior among individuals as one of the foundations of social order, and is a sociological theory with strong explanatory power. However, he ignores the influence of social environment on exchange relations, overemphasizes the selfishness and self-interest of human beings, considers human beings one-sidedly as absolutely rational, which does not conform to the objective status quo of real society, circumvents positive variables such as altruism and empathy in interpersonal relations, and ignores the panoptic influence of social class and political and economic systems. Currently, social exchange theory is the most influential conceptual paradigm for explaining organizational behavior and is widely applied in organizational behavior to explain the give-and-take relationship between leaders and employees in organizations, such as the effects of organizational support on organizational citizenship behavior, employee loyalty and job effectiveness. In organizational behavior, Blau's social exchange theory states that the relationship between employees and organizations follows the principle of reciprocity, with mutual exchange of not only tangible material resources, but also intangible ones such as symbolic approval, respect or reputation. In an exchange relationship, the giving party expects something in return from the other party, and the beneficiary also has the obligation to repay the other party. People weigh the costs and benefits of the process and decide whether to participate by choosing what is more attractive to them, whether it is a short-term or long-term reward. Most of the studies that have been conducted on employees' organizational commitment, organizational equity, organizational citizenship behavior, psychological contract, organizational trust, and hierarchical relationships in organizations have utilized the analytical framework of social exchange theory in organizations.

Neo-constructivist theory

In the context of the Internet, in the face of learning in the online environment, Mr. Wang Zhuli proposed a new constructivist theory, which argues that "learning in the Internet era faces two challenges, namely information overload and knowledge fragmentation, and proposes a zero-storage learning strategy." This theory follows the principles of classical constructivism, which states that "learning is the process of constructing meaning on top of the original knowledge." In this study, online learning behaviors emerged and developed in the context of the Internet learning era, and at the same time, the process of online learning behaviors is also a process in which online learners actively construct the meaning of knowledge. Therefore, the theory explains the background basis for the study of online learning behavior and illustrates the meaning and process of learning in the online environment.

Social cognitive theory

Social cognitive theory was proposed by Bandura, a distinguished American psychologist, who believed that "individual cognition and environment are important to behavior, and the three parties are mutually influencing and interacting".

The two-way arrows represent mutual influence and interaction, i.e., behavior is influenced by intra-individual traits and environmental factors, and at the same time, intra-individual traits and environment are also influenced by behavior. The online learning behavior is also a kind of behavior, which is also influenced by the intrapersonal traits and environment.

Theory of Rational Behavior

Rational behavior theory asserts that "an individual's behavior is determined by his or her behavioral intention, and only when an individual has a clear behavioral intention can he or she produce a specific behavior; and an individual's behavioral intention is determined by his or her attitude toward behavior and subjective norms, and only when an individual has a positive attitude toward his or her behavior and subjective norms can he or she produce a positive behavioral intention toward his or her behavior".

An individual's behavioral attitude refers to "the positive or negative emotions that an individual carries when performing a behavior", and subjective norm refers to "the subjective feelings that an individual has when choosing whether or not to perform a behavior". For example, in the study of college students' online learning behavior, whether individuals have behavioral attitudes or subjective norms towards online learning platforms or systems will affect their behavioral intentions towards online learning platforms or systems.

Online learning behavior

Learning behaviors refer to various learning-related behaviors that occur in the learning process, such as various learning activities, etc. Obviously, learning behaviors include both external behaviors that people can observe and measure, such as reading and practicing, as well as these implicit thinking activities such as memory and analysis. The subject of learning behavior is the learner, the object of behavior is various specific objects of learning behavior, which may include learning resources, learning operation objects, etc., the environment of

behavior includes learning places, learning organizations, learning rules, etc., and the means of behavior includes learning methods, etc.

However, for the relevant concepts of online learning behavior, there is no unanimously accepted definition in China, and often mentioned are online learning behavior, distance learning behavior, etc. All these concepts have similar key points, that is, learners' independent learning by using computers in the network environment. However, no matter what kind of talk is inseparable from the characteristics of online environment, autonomous learning mode, and diversity of behavior.

A domestic scholar, Lina Mei (2009), conducted a relevant study on the concept of online learning behavior and proposed that online learning behavior refers to the process of two-way interaction with the network environment that learners carry out in order to achieve certain goals. Shen Xiaoping and others studied the characteristics of online learning behavior and concluded that online learning behavior refers to the independent learning behavior carried out by learners through the network medium, using the all-round, multi-channel and interactive teaching environment constituted by computer technology and modern information communication technology, which is an important part of college students' learning behavior. Zhang et al. actively explored the types of online learning behaviors and so on from the macro level, and summarized them into three basic types: information acquisition and processing, interpersonal communication behaviors and problem solving behaviors. There are also many other related studies, such as the survey and analysis of learning behaviors of online learners (Peng et al., 2007). In summary, this study considers online learning behavior as the process of two-way interaction between learners and the online environment, drawn by a certain target learning motivation.

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In order to better address the research questions, this study adopts a combination of quantitative and qualitative research methods. In the quantitative research, the causal stepwise regression analysis proposed by Baron and Kenny (1986) is widely used in the field of education to test for mediating effects. This method is relatively simple to operate, but the test efficacy is low when the mediating effect is weak. In recent years, the rationality and validity of the causal stepwise regression analysis method have been questioned by many scholars. In this context, Preacher and Hayes (2004) proposed the Bootstrap method for testing mediating effects. Currently, the Bootstrap method has been commonly used in papers published in top international journals in the fields of psychology, business management, and organizational behavior, but domestic academic journals, especially those in the field of education, still rarely apply the Bootstrap method for testing mediating effects. However, the Bootstrap method is still rarely applied to the analysis of mediating effects in domestic academic journals, especially in the field of education. In this study, the test of mediating effects using Bootstrap analysis technique through Mplus8.0 software not only can obtain more accurate and reliable results, but also can effectively deal

with the problems of specific mediating effects and chain mediating effects of multiple mediating variables in the model of this study.

In the case study, the researcher focused on the typicality of the selected cases. Case 1 is a case in which a classroom helps college students to learn online from top to bottom by using the power of classroom teachers. In case 2, counselors and academic advisors used the opportunity of activities to promote students' online learning from the outside in. The third case is that the school teachers encourage students to form a conscious online learning from the bottom up. The three cases verify the structure and mechanism of the factors influencing college students' online learning behavior from multiple perspectives in this study. Compared with abstract theoretical concepts and data, the case studies help us to understand the highly complex processes and mechanisms of college students' online learning behaviors more deeply and to understand the rich practical logic of real actors, which is an important complement to the quantitative research results.

Conclusion

College students' online learning behavior has a rich practice in China, but the current theoretical research is unclear about what key factors influence college students' online learning behavior and the mechanisms of these influences on college students' online learning behavior. This has both affected researchers' ability to contribute unique Chinese perspectives in the field of college students' online learning behavior and limited the improvement of college students' online learning behavior practices. Based on the social exchange theory perspective, this study considers college students' online learning behavior as a social exchange process in which school teachers stimulate teachers' and students' trust and motivation through various supportive resources, which in turn promotes college students' online learning behavior. The study constructs a model of the mechanism of action with teacher-student trust and student motivation as mediating variables. After reviewing the relevant literature, this study concludes that although there are scattered studies on school teachers, teacher-student trust, and student motivation that influence college students' online learning behavior, there is a lack of operationalized scales based on the local context in China, and on the other hand, there are limited empirical studies that explore the mechanisms of school teachers' influence on college students' online learning behavior in the Chinese context. Therefore, this study will use a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to revise the existing scales to fit the local context in China and further examine the mechanisms of these influences on college students' online learning behaviors by combining data analysis and case studies with large samples.

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